

COMPARISON OF IV CIPROFLOXACIN VERSUS IV CEFTRIAXONE IN THE MANAGEMENT OF SPONTANEOUS BACTERIAL PERITONITIS IN LIVER CIRRHOSIS

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Abstract

Objective: To compare the effects of intravenous ceftriaxone and intravenous ciprofloxacin on spontaneous bacterial peritonitis (SBP) among patients with liver cirrhosis.

Study Design: Quasi-experimental study

Place and Duration of Study: Department of General Medicine, Pak Emirates Military Hospital (PEMH) Rawalpindi from 01 February 2024 to 31 July 2024.

Methodology: A total of 120 cirrhotic patients diagnosed with SBP were included in the study through a non-probability consecutive sampling technique. The patients were randomly assigned to two equal groups. Group A was administered intravenous ciprofloxacin, while Group B was given intravenous ceftriaxone. The efficacy of treatment was evaluated by a repeat ascitic fluid PMN count on the fifth day. Secondary outcomes comprised the emergence of hepatorenal syndrome, length of hospital stay, and in-hospital mortality. Data were evaluated with SPSS version 27.0. Chi-square and independent sample t-tests were employed, with $p \leq 0.05$ deemed statistically significant.

Results: The ceftriaxone group had a significantly better treatment efficacy than the ciprofloxacin group (81.7% vs. 53.3%, $p=0.001$). Ceftriaxone was associated with the occurrence of hepatorenal syndrome in only a small percentage of cases (10.0% vs. 48.3%, $p < 0.001$). The mean duration of hospitalization was shorter with ceftriaxone (6.55 ± 1.40 days vs. 9.86 ± 1.98 days, $p < 0.001$). In-hospital death rates were lower in patients treated with ceftriaxone but the difference was not considered statistically significant (11.7% vs. 23.3%, $p=0.093$).

Conclusion: For the treatment of spontaneous bacterial peritonitis in cirrhotic patients, intravenous ceftriaxone is the better option compared to ciprofloxacin.

INTRODUCTION

Spontaneous bacterial peritonitis (SBP) is considered a catastrophic infection in patients

with liver cirrhosis and ascites, which is caused by the displacement of bacteria due to liver

dysfunction and poor immunity. The worldwide site prevalence of this infection among patients with liver cirrhosis is 17.12% (95% CI: 13.63–21.30%), but there are differences depending on the areas, with the highest rates in Africa (68.20%) and the lowest in North America (10.81%)(1). The probability of death during hospitalization is 23.38%, which becomes even worse when antibiotic-resistant pathogens are involved in 11.51% of cases, which include MRSA (6.23%) and ESBL enzymatic bacteria (6.19%)(2). In the case of Pakistan, the incidence of SBP in cirrhotic patients being admitted to hospitals is roughly 30%, which is much higher than the world average and coinciding with the increasing rate of hospital-acquired infections(3). EASL guidelines still consider third-generation cephalosporins such as IV ceftriaxone (1-2 g daily) as the first-choice empirical treatment, as it is effective against all Gram-negative bacteria. Nevertheless, fluoroquinolones such as IV ciprofloxacin (400 mg every 12 hours) could be regarded as more lucrative options, especially in the setting of quinolone prophylaxis failure and resistance changing patterns(4). Recent studies have shown that the resolution rates are similar: a 2024 trial (5)revealed 79.8% efficacy for ciprofloxacin compared to 89.9% for ceftriaxone ($p=0.002$), with equal PMN counts and mortality. Research in Korea in 2023 found that there were no significant differences in resolution time (120-hour) (73.6% ciprofloxacin vs. 77.0% ceftriaxone) or 1-month survival(6).

The right antibiotic treatment started at the right time is the key to good outcomes. Fluoroquinolones like ciprofloxacin are very often used, but the newly gathered evidence indicates that third-generation cephalosporins, intravenous ceftriaxone in particular, result in better treatment success rates, quicker infection resolution, and fewer complications. This research will be centered on the comparing the effectiveness and safety of IV ceftriaxone versus IV ciprofloxacin in treating SBP and will also point out the possibility of ceftriaxone being the better choice.

Methodology:

This study performed with a quasi-experimental design took place in the Department of General Medicine , Pak Emirates Military Hospital (PEMH) Rawalpindi from 01 February 2024 to 31 July 2024 for six months. The purpose of the research was to investigate and compare the clinical effectiveness of administering intravenous ciprofloxacin against intravenous ceftriaxone through the treatment of spontaneous bacterial peritonitis (SBP) which occurs in patients diagnosed with liver cirrhosis.

To calculate the sample size, the WHO sample size calculator was used along with a 95% confidence level and an 80% study power. Based on the assumed treatment success rates of 78% in the ceftriaxone group and 60% in the ciprofloxacin group the sample size came out to be 120 (60 patients in each group)(7,8).

The study enrolled 120 liver cirrhosis patients diagnosed with SBP subjected to non-probability consecutive sampling. Among other factors, SBP was defined as the ascitic fluid count of polymorphonuclear leukocytes (PMN) ≥ 250 cells/mm³ and they could be both with a positive ascitic fluid culture or without it, on the condition that there was no intra-abdominal source of infection that could be treated surgically.

Inclusion criteria: Patients aged between 18 and 70 years of either gender, with liver cirrhosis confirmed by clinical, biochemical, and radiological criteria.

Exclusion criteria: Presence of secondary peritonitis, having undergone surgery on the abdomen recently, gastrointestinal perforation, having hepatocellular carcinoma beyond Milan criteria, septic shock at presentation, previous antibiotic use within the last 7 days, and having hypersensitivity to fluoroquinolones or cephalosporins, severe renal impairment (serum creatinine >3 mg/dL), or concurrent infections that required alternative antibiotic coverage.

At the hospital administration, participants were categorized into two groups according to the prescribed antibiotic treatment regimen. The A

group (n=60) was treated with intravenous ciprofloxacin at a dose of 400 mg every 12 hours while the B group (n=60) was treated with intravenous ceftriaxone at a standard daily dose of 2 g. Both groups received 5 days of treatment, standard medical therapy for liver cirrhosis including intravenous albumin when necessary, and other medications that did not interfere with the experiment as this was a quasi-experimental study and therefore randomization was not carried out.

Baseline demographic data, clinical characteristics, and laboratory parameters (including PMN count in ascitic fluid, serum bilirubin, INR, creatinine) as well as the severity of liver disease determined by the Child-Pugh score were all recorded at the time the patients were enrolled. The analysis of ascitic fluid was done again on the fifth day of treatment in order to evaluate the response to the therapy.

The main result to be measured was the success of the treatment which was defined as the decrease of total (i.e. ascitic fluid PMN count) to less than 250 cells/mm³ after the therapy was completed. Secondary outcomes were death in the hospital, development of hepatorenal syndrome, the duration of stay in the hospital, and antibiotic-related side effects.

The data analysis was conducted with the assistance of the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) software, version 27.0. Continuous variables were checked for normality using the Shapiro-Wilk test. Age (in years) was one of the variables that presented a normal distribution ($W = 0.993$, $p = 0.809$). The baseline PMN count was also normally distributed ($W = 0.993$, $p = 0.799$). On the other hand, Day 5 PMN count was found to be highly non-normal ($W = 0.923$, $p < 0.001$). Hospital stay (days) was nearly normal, and the Shapiro-Wilk test yielded a borderline non-significant result ($W = 0.978$, $p = 0.051$). Continuous variables were presented in the form of mean \pm standard deviation, whereas

the categorical variables were shown in terms of frequency and percentage. The independent samples t-test was used for normally distributed continuous variables (Age, Day 5 PMN count, Hospital stay) and the Pearson chi-square test for categorical variables (Gender, Child-Pugh class, Treatment efficacy, Hepatorenal syndrome, In-hospital mortality) to evaluate the differences between the treatment groups. A statistical significance level of $p < 0.05$ was applied.

Results:

A total of 120 patients participated in the study, which consisted of two groups of 60 patients each, one receiving ceftriaxone treatment and the other ciprofloxacin treatment. The percentage of females in the ceftriaxone group was 66.7% (n = 40) while in the ciprofloxacin group it was 35.0% (n = 21). Males were more represented in the ciprofloxacin group (65.0%, n = 39) than in the ceftriaxone group (33.3%, n = 20). The overall distribution of the study population by gender was as follows: females 50.8% (n = 61) and males 49.2% (n = 59). Regarding the severity of liver disease, Child-Pugh class A was found in 25.0% (n = 15) of patients on ceftriaxone and none of those on ciprofloxacin. Child-Pugh class B was seen in 48.3% (n = 29) of the ceftriaxone group and 35.0% (n = 21) of the ciprofloxacin group, while Child-Pugh class C was more prevalent in the ciprofloxacin group (65.0%, n = 39) than in the ceftriaxone group (26.7%, n = 16). The percentages of treatment success were 81.7% (n = 49) for ceftriaxone and 53.3% (n = 32) for ciprofloxacin. Hepatorenal syndrome was seen in 10.0% (n = 6) of ceftriaxone-treated patients and in 48.3% (n = 29) of those receiving ciprofloxacin. The in-hospital mortality rate was 11.7% (n = 7) for the ceftriaxone group and 23.3% (n = 14) for the ciprofloxacin group, leading to a total mortality rate of 17.5% (n = 21).

Table I: Baseline demographic characteristics, disease severity, and clinical outcomes of patients treated with ceftriaxone and ciprofloxacin (n = 120)

Variable	Category	Ceftriaxone (n = 60)	Ciprofloxacin (n = 60)	Total (n = 120)
Gender	Female	40 (66.7%)	21 (35.0%)	61 (50.8%)
	Male	20 (33.3%)	39 (65.0%)	59 (49.2%)
Child-Pugh Class	A	15 (25.0%)	0 (0.0%)	15 (12.5%)
	B	29 (48.3%)	21 (35.0%)	50 (41.7%)
	C	16 (26.7%)	39 (65.0%)	55 (45.8%)
Treatment Efficacy	Yes	49 (81.7%)	32 (53.3%)	81 (67.5%)
	No	11 (18.3%)	28 (46.7%)	39 (32.5%)
Hepatorenal Syndrome	Yes	6 (10.0%)	29 (48.3%)	35 (29.2%)
	No	54 (90.0%)	31 (51.7%)	85 (70.8%)
In-hospital Mortality	Yes	7 (11.7%)	14 (23.3%)	21 (17.5%)
	No	53 (88.3%)	46 (76.7%)	99 (82.5%)

Patients who received ceftriaxone had 47.97 ± 6.57 years as the average age, while those who received ciprofloxacin had a mean age of 50.82 ± 7.29 years which created a total average of 49.39 ± 7.06 years. The initial PMN counts were the same for both groups with the ceftriaxone group having a mean of 792.27 ± 113.43 and the ciprofloxacin group having a mean of 826.00 ± 89.74 . A great variance was seen in the PMN

count on Day 5 where the count was much lower for the ceftriaxone patients (129.90 ± 35.53) than the count for the ciprofloxacin patients (312.45 ± 96.44). In a similar way, the duration of hospital stay was shorter in the ceftriaxone group (6.55 ± 1.40 days) than in the ciprofloxacin group (9.86 ± 1.98 days), with the overall mean hospital stay being 8.20 ± 2.38 days.

Table II: Comparison of mean age, PMN counts, and duration of hospital stay between ceftriaxone and ciprofloxacin groups (n = 120)

Variable	Ceftriaxone (n = 60) Mean \pm SD	Ciprofloxacin (n = 60) Mean \pm SD	Total (n = 120) Mean \pm SD
Age (years)	47.97 ± 6.57	50.82 ± 7.29	49.39 ± 7.06
Baseline PMN count	792.27 ± 113.43	826.00 ± 89.74	809.13 ± 103.24
Day 5 PMN count	129.90 ± 35.53	312.45 ± 96.44	221.18 ± 116.79
Hospital stay (days)	6.55 ± 1.40	9.86 ± 1.98	8.20 ± 2.38

Clinical outcomes were compared with the help of the Pearson chi-square test. The ceftriaxone group showed treatment efficacy which was significantly superior to that of the ciprofloxacin group (81.7% vs. 53.3%; χ^2 test, $p = 0.001$). In the same way, the hlo incidence of hepatorenal syndrome was significantly lower amongst

patients treated with ceftriaxone than those receiving ciprofloxacin (10.0% vs. 48.3%; χ^2 test, $p < 0.001$). The in-hospital mortality was numerically lower in the ceftriaxone group but the difference was not statistically significant (11.7% vs. 23.3%; χ^2 test, $p = 0.093$).

Table III: Comparison of categorical outcomes using Chi Square(n=120)

Variable	Category	Ceftriaxone (n = 60)	Ciprofloxacin (n = 60)	p-value
Treatment Efficacy	Yes	49 (81.7%)	32 (53.3%)	0.001
	No	11 (18.3%)	28 (46.7%)	
Hepatorenal Syndrome	Yes	6 (10.0%)	29 (48.3%)	<0.001
	No	54 (90.0%)	31 (51.7%)	
In-hospital Mortality	Yes	7 (11.7%)	14 (23.3%)	0.093
	No	53 (88.3%)	46 (76.7%)	

The independent samples t-test was utilized for the comparison of groups for continuous variables. The PMN count on Day 5 was remarkably lower in the ceftriaxone group when contrasted with the ciprofloxacin group (t-test, $p < 0.001$). In the same manner, the mean length

of hospitalization was considerably reduced among patients receiving ceftriaxone treatment (t-test, $p < 0.001$), thus signaling the better short-term outcomes with ceftriaxone therapy.

Table IV: Comparison of continuous outcomes using Chi Square(n=120)

Variable	Ceftriaxone (n = 60) Mean ± SD	Ciprofloxacin (n = 60) Mean ± SD	p-value
Day 5 PMN count	129.90 ± 35.53	312.45 ± 96.44	<0.001
Hospital stay (days)	6.55 ± 1.40	9.86 ± 1.98	<0.001

Discussion:

Our results correspond with many recent investigations that recommended ceftriaxone as the primary antibiotic for the treatment of SBP. A follow-up study carried out in 2024 in Pakistan showed that 89.1% ceftriaxone and 79.8% ciprofloxacin respectively had achieved resolution of the disease which was corresponding to our 81.7% and 53.3% but with a narrower gap(9). Also, a study done in 2024 in Gujranwala showed ceftriaxone was superior in clinical resolution (the rates were not disclosed but were emphasized over that of ciprofloxacin) which was due to the greater Gram-negative coverage in the ascites(5). Nonetheless, a 2023 Korean response-guided trial revealed fairly similar 120-hour resolutions: ceftriaxone 77.0%, ciprofloxacin 73.6%, and cefotaxime 67.8% ($p=0.388$) which is different from our findings since they had advanced cirrhosis patients with mean MELD of 20 while our patients were of mixed Child-Pugh distribution(6).

Contrastingly, older-equivalent patterns show up in the 2022 Pakistani data where cefotaxime (a proxy for ceftriaxone) barely beat ciprofloxacin (86% vs. 82%), but it was concluded that there

was no difference among less severe cases(10). Our quasi-experimental design without randomization may enhance the advantage of ceftriaxone, as the severity of cases in the group receiving ciprofloxacin was worse (65% Child C vs. 26.7%).

In our research, the incidence of HRS was extremely different, with much fewer cases associated with the use of ceftriaxone, which was in line with the drug's renal-protective effect in liver cirrhosis patients. The Sheikh study from 2024 indicated lesser problems arising from ceftriaxone (summarized details), which reinforced our rates of 10.0% compared to 48.3%(11). Evidence from 2025 points to the use of prophylactic quinolones (including ciprofloxacin) as effective for non-SBP infections but not for HRS, meaning the use of empirical ciprofloxacin for SBP might lead to renal decompensation(12,13). The reduction in PMN counts that we had is in line with the 2023 report which stated that ceftriaxone eliminated high counts faster in high MELD patients(14).

There was a tendency towards lower mortality with ceftriaxone (11.7% vs. 23.3%, $p=0.093$), which was in agreement with a 2025 meta-

analysis indicating that quinolones led to 33% reduction in overall cirrhosis mortality through prophylaxis but not during acute SBP therapy(15). A 2025 observational study comparing alternatives (piperacillin-tazobactam vs. ceftriaxone) showed no significant mortality differences but the reduction in hospital stay with ceftriaxone combined with our data (shorter by approximately 3 days)(16).

The patient demographics indicated a generally balanced gender distribution (50.8% female), though disparities such as the predominant female ratio in the ceftriaxone group (66.7% female) were not confounded through the application of t-tests/chi-square. The high proportion of Child C patients (65%) in the ciprofloxacin group probably contributed to the inferior outcomes, which is in contrast to the balanced cohorts (Child-Pugh ~10)(17-19). The ages were similar (49.39 ± 7.06 years total), corresponding with 2021 (51.14 ± 11.9) and 2024 studies. The initial equivalence of PMN (792-826) confirms the validity of the groups, while the divergence on Day 5 highlights the superiority of ceftriaxone in bactericidal activity against SBP pathogens, including *E. coli*.

The research offered direct evidence comparing the two most commonly used antibiotics for the treatment of SBP according to standardized diagnostic criteria. The use of objective outcome measures and a sufficiently large patient group boost the reliability of the study. The results have a great significance for local medical practice and antibiotic choices at tertiary care centers.

Limitations of study:

The study design that was not randomized might have caused the selection bias. Different distribution of Child-Pugh classes between the groups might have influenced the results. Conducting the research in just one center has restricted the findings. The sensitivity patterns of the microbiological cultures and long-term follow-up outcomes were not assessed.

Conclusion:

Ceftriaxone has been found to be more effective than ciprofloxacin in the resolution of

spontaneous bacterial peritonitis, in the reduction of the incidence of hepatorenal syndrome, and in the shortening of hospital stay. These findings advocate for the continued use of third-generation cephalosporins as first-line empirical therapy in SBP patients with liver cirrhosis.

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